

STUDYING THE MOTIVATION OF SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURS IN KAZAKHSTAN

*Aukenov Ye.**DBA Student, Almaty Management University
Almaty, Kazakhstan***Abstract**

This article presents the qualitative results of in-depth interviews with social entrepreneurs included in the Register of Social Entrepreneurship Entities in Kazakhstan in order to fill a gap in the scientific literature on social entrepreneurship and to lay an empirical basis for further research on the motivation of social entrepreneurs.

Keywords: social entrepreneurship, motivation of social entrepreneurs, portrait of a social entrepreneur, definition of social entrepreneurship.

Introduction. Social entrepreneurship is becoming an increasingly popular phenomenon in which business approaches are applied to solving social problems. But who are social entrepreneurs, and what motivates them? What made them involve in social entrepreneurship, and why did they choose this path despite the fact that social enterprises generate less income compared to traditional business? These questions remain among the least studied today.

Most of the academic literature related to social entrepreneurship is devoted to the correct interpretation of terminology and the problems that social entrepreneurs face. More in-depth research papers focus on various narrow issues of social entrepreneurship, such as funding, sustainability, organizational structure, innovativeness, etc. And only a few studies are devoted to the study of what motivates individuals and companies to position themselves as social enterprises.

This article presents qualitative results of in-depth interviews with social entrepreneurs included in the Register of Social Entrepreneurship Organizations in Kazakhstan. The main aim is to contribute to filling the gap in the academic literature on social entrepreneurship and laying an empirical basis for further research on the motivation of social entrepreneurs.

The concept of social entrepreneurship. Despite the fact that social entrepreneurship has been actively developing around the world for several decades, as of today there is no universal definition of this term. Scientists have made many attempts to give an exhaustive definition of the concepts of "social entrepreneurship" and "social entrepreneur" [1, 2, 3, 4], however in the academic literature none of them has become commonly accepted. Just as in the scientific literature, there is neither a standard definition of social entrepreneurship in legislative acts: the legislation of different countries approaches the definition and classification of organizations related to social entrepreneurship in different ways [5].

In addition to the absence of a universal definition, there is also no consensus on the usage of terminology related to social entrepreneurship. Referring to the organizations that work in this sphere, the authors interchangeably use such terms as "social business", "social enterprise", "organizations in the social sphere", "social-oriented organization", etc. [6].

Nonetheless, if we summarize the different definitions of social entrepreneurship, the main characteristics that these organizations possess can be highlighted.

In particular, organizations that are referred to as social enterprises are those whose main goal is to create social benefits or solve social problems using the tools and mechanisms that are used by traditional business enterprises. Thus, social enterprises are organizations that have the characteristics of traditional entrepreneurship in terms of organizational structure and activities, but do not pursue the goal of maximizing profits and are aimed at solving social problems.

Theories of motivation for commercial entrepreneurs and non-profit organizations. As follows from the definition above, social entrepreneurs possess characteristics of both private business entities and third sector organizations (non-profit organizations). Therefore, in what comes below the theories regarding the motivation of organizations of both sectors shall be considered.

The issue of motivation for commercial entrepreneurs has been comprehensively studied by a number of researchers. There are many different theories and academic literature on this topic. In general, scientists identify several main factors that motivate people to start their own business.

First of all, it is a factor of demands or a factor of basic vital needs [7]. For example, the basic need to have an income to support themselves and their families is one of the reasons why people start their own business, even if such a business does not generate much profit [8].

Secondly, it is the need for self-realization. People who start their own business often feel happy only when they have their own business, can work independently and realize their potential [9].

Thirdly, based on the results of empirical research, scientists highlight such a factor in the motivation of entrepreneurs as the need for achievements [10]. According to Hansemark, the entrepreneur's need for achievement is associated with his desire to do something faster and better than others, or than himself in the past [11]. Researchers note that such people set clear goals for themselves, engage in advance planning, take responsibility for their actions and expect an immediate effect from their entrepreneurial activities [12].

People working in the third sector organizations are also often motivated in their work, despite lower financial rewards than in commercial organizations [13]. Thus, theories of motivation in the third sector are applied somewhat differently than with traditional entre-

preneurs. In addition to the theories of need and demands, scientists identify such features of motivation in the third sector as high involvement in organizational activities [14], a call or a sense of civic duty [13], a desire to participate in political decision-making, devotion to public goals, and high level of compassion and empathy [15].

Therefore, given that social entrepreneurship has the characteristics of both commercial entrepreneurship and third sector organizations, it can be assumed that the motivation of social entrepreneurs should also be similar to the motivation of the mentioned areas.

Research objectives. The main goal of this study was to find answers to the following key questions:

1) What is the profile of a social entrepreneur in Kazakhstan today?

2) What motivates social entrepreneurs to involve in social entrepreneurship instead of following more established career paths that seem more stable and predictable?

3) Are there similarities in the motivation of social entrepreneurs and the motivation of commercial entrepreneurs and people engaged in the third sector?

Methodology. To get answers to the research questions mentioned above, a sociological method of

conducting research was chosen. In particular, ten in-depth qualitative interviews were conducted with the organizations included in the Register of Social Entrepreneurship Organizations of Kazakhstan. At the time when the interviews were held, there were 25 organizations included in the Register [16]. The interviews were conducted with 40% of them, thus the results of the study can be considered as representative and reliable.

The selection of participants was made on the principle of representation of different regions of Kazakhstan and the scope of their professional activities and, of course, their accessibility. In-depth interviews were conducted from June to August, 2022 based on the pre-prepared interview form. The interviews were conducted via the Zoom platform.

Key findings.

Profile of a social entrepreneur in Kazakhstan.

The study involved both those who have been engaged in social entrepreneurship for more than 20 years, and those who formalized their status less than a year ago. The age range of entrepreneurs is also very wide: there are young people aged 23 as well as people over the age of 60. This suggests that social entrepreneurship in Kazakhstan is a subject of interest for people of all ages.

Figure 1. Age of social entrepreneurs

The majority of respondents (eight out of ten) have a higher education, two respondents have a secondary specialized education. A similar situation is observed with regard to marital status: eight out of ten participants are married, two respondents are not married. Nine out of ten participants have children.

Out of ten social entrepreneurs that participated in the study eight belong to the vulnerable groups of population, solving whose problems is the main goal of social entrepreneurs according to the Entrepreneurial Code of Kazakhstan [17]. Hence, it can be concluded that 80% of people involved in social entrepreneurship came to this area to solve the problems that they personally encountered.

All of the organizations that participated in the interviews are small enterprises with no more than 50 employees and with a profitability of no more than 20 million tenge per year. The average salary of workers in social enterprises varies from 100,000 to 250,000 tenge per month.

Motivation of social entrepreneurs. As a result of the interviews, it was found out that there are several factors that motivate social entrepreneurs to establish a social enterprise.

The first factor is the professional interest. Two out of ten respondents said that they decided to become social entrepreneurs because in the course of their professional career. The main factor that served as an impetus for the opening of the social enterprise for these respondents was the high compassion and concern for the problems of vulnerable groups of the population.

Three out of ten participants also answered that their main motivation was the desire to help socially vulnerable groups of the population with employment, social rehabilitation and integration into society. It is worth mentioning that two of them have large families with more than four children, while the other one is a single mother bringing up children on her own.

"In 2015, I got on a bus and saw people who were deaf and mute having an argument. I became interested

in how they live, how they earn money, how they communicate, how they create families. I immediately went to the Employment Center and asked if there were people with disabilities who were looking for work. The reason was that they are socially vulnerable, and it is even more difficult for them to find a job than for everyone else.” (excerpt from an interview).

“There are many social projects but no one wants to engage in them, because commercial business generates income, whereas social entrepreneurship is a different philosophy. It needs to be developed and we need to talk about it more often. It is very difficult to work with socially vulnerable groups of population. This is a very big responsibility and a social ideology” (excerpt from an interview).

Five out of ten participants said that they decided to become social entrepreneurs because they faced a personal problem. Two of them are themselves people with disabilities of first and second group, while the other three have children with disabilities.

“I came to social entrepreneurship because I faced a personal problem. I have a child with disability (autism spectrum disorder)” (excerpt from the interview).

“We both have physical disabilities, we know all the problems and difficulties” (excerpt from an interview).

“I have a child with a disability, and since I understood that the services provided by state organizations do not meet our requirements, I decided to engage in educational activities for special children” (excerpt from an interview).

Conclusions. As a result of the in-depth interviews, it was found out that social entrepreneurs in Kazakhstan have a wide range of age categories and work experience as a social entrepreneur. Most of the respondents have higher education, are married and have children. Also, 80% of respondents belong to the socially vulnerable groups of the population, at which the activities of social entrepreneurship entities are aimed in accordance with the Entrepreneurial Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

The main motivation factors for Kazakhstani social entrepreneurs were personal experience as persons belonging to vulnerable groups, as well as a high level of compassion and a desire to help solve social problems. None of the respondents noted the factors that scientists identify as motivating commercial entrepreneurs (factors of financial need, the need for self-realization and achievement). Thus, we can conclude that in terms of motivation, social entrepreneurs are more similar to non-profit or third sector organizations than to traditional entrepreneurs.

It should be noted that the conducted study has certain shortcomings, such as a limited sample, the lack of quantitative data and control groups, as well as the inability to extrapolate the results of a qualitative study to all social entrepreneurship entities. Nevertheless, this study can become a platform for further deeper empirical research in this area.

References

1. Brooks, A. C. (2009). *Social Entrepreneurship: A Modern Approach to Social Value Creation*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson.
2. Germak, A. J., and Singh, K. K. (2010). Social Entrepreneurship: Changing the Way Social Workers do Business. *Administration in Social Work* 34 (1): 79–95
3. Kickul, J., and Lyons, T. S. (2012). *Understanding Social Entrepreneurship: The Relentless Pursuit of Mission in an Ever Changing World*. New York: Routledge.
4. Zahra, S. A., Gedajlovic, E., Neubaum, D. O., and Shulman, J. M. (2009). A Typology of Social Entrepreneurs: Motives, Search Processes, and Ethical Challenges. *Journal of Business Venturing* 24: 519–532.
5. Kerlin, J. A. (2010). A Comparative Analysis of the Global Emergence of Social Enterprise. *Voluntas: International Journal of Voluntary and Nonprofit Organizations* 21 (2): 162–179
6. Germak, A.J., and Robinson, J. A. (2014). Exploring the Motivation of Nascent Social Entrepreneurs, *Journal of Social Entrepreneurship*, 5:1, 5-21, DOI:10.1080/19420676.2013.820781
7. Zankis, S. H., Renko, M., and Bullough, A. (2012). Nascent Entrepreneurs and the Transition to Entrepreneurship: Why do People Start New Businesses? *Journal of Developmental Entrepreneurship* 17 (1): 1–25.
8. Hessels, J., van Gelderen, M., and Thurik, R. (2008). Entrepreneurial Aspirations, Motivations, and their Drivers. *Small Business Economics* 31: 323–339
9. Maslow, A. H. (1943). A Theory of Human Motivation. *Psychological Review* 50: 370–396.
10. McClelland, D. C. (1965). Achievement and Entrepreneurship: A Longitudinal Study. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 1: 389–392.
11. Hansemark, O. C. (1998). The Effects of an Entrepreneurship Programme on Need for Achievement and Locus of Control of Reinforcement. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research* 4 (1): 28–50.
12. Barba-Sanchez, V., and Atienza-Sahuquillo, C. (2011). Reasons to Create a New Venture: A Determinant of Entrepreneurial Profiles. *African Journal of Business Management* 5 (28): 11497–11504.
13. Denhardt, R. B., Denhardt, J. V., and Aristigueta M. P. (2009). *Managing Human Behavior in Public and Nonprofit Organizations*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
14. Lawler, E. E. (1990). *High Involvement Management*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
15. Perry, J. L. (1996). Measuring Public Service Motivation: An Assessment of Construct Reliability and Validity. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory* 6 (1): 5–22.
16. Official website of the Ministry of National Economy of the Republic of Kazakhstan. URL: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/economy/documents/1?lang=ru> [accessed on November 30, 2022].
17. The Entrepreneurial Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Article 232-1. URL: <https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/K1500000375#z2343> [accessed on November 30, 2022].